

BIOGEOGRAPHY FROM SPACE – A NEW TOOL TO DISENTANGLE IBERIAN FORESTS ECOLOGY AND DISTRIBUTION IN IBERIAN PENINSULA

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INTRODUCTION

Iberian Peninsula

583,832 km²

Biogeographically - almost-island

Europe vs Africa

Atlantic vs Mediterranean

Fig. 1.1 The Iberian Peninsula with its main structural units

Loidi, J. (2017). Introduction to the Iberian Peninsula, General Features: Geography, Geology, Name, Brief History, Land Use and Conservation. In *The Vegetation of the Iberian Peninsula* (pp. 3-27). Springer, Cham.

INTRODUCTION

J. Loidi

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INTRODUCTION

http://www.globalbioclimatics.org/form/tb_map/index.htm

Fig. 2.5 Macrobioclimates and bioclimates in the Iberian Peninsula and Balearic Islands

2.1.2 Parameters and Bioclimatic Indices

The most common bioclimatic parameters and indices used in our bioclimatic classification are detailed below (a more detailed list in Rivas-Martínez et al. 2011a). The list starts with precipitation parameters (rainfall expressed in mm), followed by temperature parameters (with averages in degrees Celsius and positive temperature of indices in tenths of degrees Celsius), seasonality, ending with the bioclimatic indices which are simple arithmetic formulas that include parameters.

Precipitation Parameters

- P average annual precipitation in millimetres or litres per square metre.
- P_i average monthly precipitation, where i : 1 = January, ..., 12 = December.
- P_{cm_1} precipitation of the warmest four consecutive months of the year.
- P_{cm_2} precipitation of the four consecutive months following the warmest of the year.
- P_{cm_3} precipitation of the four consecutive months before the warmest of the year.
- P_d precipitation of the driest quarter of the year.
- P_p positive annual precipitation of the months with T_i higher than 0°C , $\sum P_{p_i} > 0^\circ\text{C}$.
- P_s precipitation for the summer quarter.
- P_{ss} precipitation for the warmest six consecutive months of the year.
- P_{sw} precipitation for the coldest six consecutive months of the year.
- P_w precipitation for the winter quarter.

Temperature Parameters

- T mean annual temperature in centigrade.
- T_i mean monthly temperature in centigrades, where i : 1 = January, ..., 12 = December.
- T_{min} average temperature of the coldest month of the year in $^\circ\text{C}$.
- T_p positive annual temperature. Total in tenths of degrees Celsius of the average monthly temperatures higher than 0°C , $\sum T_{p_i} > 0^\circ\text{C}$.
- T_{p_i} positive monthly temperature, where i : 1 = January, ..., 12 = December, in tenths of degrees Celsius.
- T_{ps} positive temperature of the summer quarter, in tenths of degrees Celsius, $\sum T_{ps_i} > 0^\circ\text{C}$.
- T_{pw} positive temperature of the coldest quarter, in tenths of degrees Celsius, $\sum T_{pw_i} > 0^\circ\text{C}$.
- T_s average temperature of the summer quarter, N: T 6–8, S T 12–2.
- M average temperature of the maximums of the coldest month.
- m average temperature of the minimums of the coldest month.
- m_i average monthly temperature of the minimums, where i : 1 = January, ..., 12 = December.

INTRODUCTION

Rivas Goday, S. (1956). Übersicht über die Vegetationsgürtel der iberischen Halbinsel. kennzeichnende Arten und Gesellschaften. *Veröff. Ber. Geobot. Inst. Rübel in Zürich*, 31(1), 32-69.

Rivas-Martínez, S., Penas, Á., del Río, S., González, T. E. D., & Rivas-Sáenz, S. (2017). Bioclimatology of the Iberian Peninsula and the Balearic Islands. In *The Vegetation of the Iberian Peninsula* (pp. 29-80). Springer, Cham.

INTRODUCTION

Underlying factors - transitional (ecotone) areas - 2 major biogeographic ecoregions

Submediterranean Ecotone

INTRODUCTION - MARCESCENT FORESTS - ECOTONE

- Termophilous Lauroid (Mid-Tertiary) vegetation
- Mesophytic Paleoclimatic relicts (lauroid elements)
- *Rhododendron ponticum*
- *Myrica faia*
- *Quercus canariensis*
- *Laurus nobilis*
- *Frangula alnus* subsp. *baetica*
- *Prunus lusitanica*

OBJECTIVES

- Use species distribution models (SDMs)

- Oaks (*Quercus* L.)

- Functional groups (Deciduous and Marcescent)

Vs

- Species geographic references retrieve climatic envelopes (minimum thresholds of P and T)

- Assess the contribution of remote sensing variables beside classic climatic ?

FOCAL SPECIES AND OCCURRENCE DATA (DECIDUOUS VS MARCESCENT)

- Section *Quercus* Linnaeus (1753: 994); Nixon & Muller (1997); Denk et. al. (2017: 13) (= Sect. *Robur* Loudon (1838: 1730))

Subsection *Galliferae* (Spach) Gurke
(≡ Section *Galliferae* Spach (1842: 170))

FOCAL SPECIES AND OCCURRENCE DATA

Quercus estremadurensis O.Schwarz

Quercus orocantabrica Rivas Mart. & al.

Quercus petraea (Matt.) Liebl.

Quercus pubescens Willd.

Quercus pyrenaica Willd.

Quercus robur L.

Quercus x rosacea Bechst.

- **Section *Quercus*** Linnaeus (1753: 994); Nixon & Muller (1997); Denk et. al. (2017: 13) (= **Sect. *Robur*** Loudon (1838: 1730))

FOCAL SPECIES AND OCCURRENCE DATA

Quercus broteroi (Cout.) Rivas Mart. & Sáenz de Rivas

Quercus canariensis Willd.

Quercus faginea Lam

Quercus lusitanica Lam.

Quercus marianica C. Vicioso

Quercus subpyrenaica Villar

Quercus × *cerrioides* Willk. & Costa

- Subsection *Galliferae* (Spach) Gurke
(≡ Section *Galliferae* Spach (1842: 170))

METHODS AND TOOLS - DATA COLLECTION (TACKLING TAXONOMIC UNCERTAINTY)

- Fieldwork (2006-present)
- 16 Reference herbaria, (specimens revision – full collections) + Field Work
- Online collections (B; G-BOIS, K, MAIA, MNHN-P, MPU & P-LAM)
- Cryptic literature (Floras / Geobotany)

Leaf persistence type	Species	Records
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus pyrenaica</i>	7786
Deciduous	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	1580
Deciduous	<i>Quercus robur</i>	1387
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	1073
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus subpyrenaica</i>	725
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus faginea</i>	568
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus broteroi</i>	533
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus lusitanica</i>	360
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus marianica</i>	90
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus estremadurensis</i>	70
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus canariensis</i>	69
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus x cerrioides</i>	68
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus x rosaceae</i>	47
Marcrescent	<i>Quercus x coutinhoi</i>	29
Deciduous	<i>Quercus orocantabria</i>	28

METHODS AND TOOLS

- **Species Distribution Models (SDMs) | 1 km UTM**
- **BIOMOD2** – a platform for ensemble forecasting of species distributions models
- **10 modelling techniques** (GLM', 'GBM', 'GAM', 'CTA', 'ANN', 'FDA', 'MARS', 'RF', 'MAXENT.Phillips', MAXENT.Tsuruoka“
- **Current period (WorldClim1.4).**

- **9 Environmental Variables Tested for non-parametric correlation (score <0.7)**

3 Temp / BIO1 = Annual Mean Temperature / BIO4 = Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation *100) / BIO6 = Min Temperature of Coldest Month

2 Pp / BIO12 = Annual Precipitation / BIO18 = Precipitation of Warmest Quarter

- **1 TOPO / TWI = WETNESS INDEX**

RS VARIABLES

✓ – Terra/MODIS High frequency image collection Satellites (>1 image/d)

ANNUAL INDICATORS (2001-2017):

- PRODUCTIVITY | EVI MEDIAN
- SEASONALITY EVI INTRA-ANUAL VARIATION
- PHENOLOGY EVI DAY OF MAXIMUM

RESULTS – MODELS PERFORMANCE (TSS)

RESULTS – VARIABLE CONTRIBUTIONS

BIO6 = Min Temperature of Coldest Month

BIO4 = Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation * 100)

BIO18 = Precipitation of Warmest Quarter

BIO12 = Annual Precipitation

RS Variables (8/15 taxa) second most important

EVI median (Productivity)

EVI DAY OF MAXIMUM (PHENOLOGY)

RESULTS & DISCUSSION—TEMPERATE

Quercus orocantabrica

Quercus robur

Quercus petraea

0 200 Km

RESULTS & DISCUSSION – SUBMEDITERRANEAN

RESULTS & DISCUSSION – SUBMEDITERRANEAN BELT

BIOCLIMATIC BASED

MODEL BASED (MARCESCENT SPECIES)

[De Dios et al., 2006](#)

RESULTS & DISCUSSION – TEMPERATE VS SUBMEDITERRANEAN

Temperate Belt (Deciduous)

Submediterranean Belt (Marcescent)

RESULTS & DISCUSSION – LIFE ZONES/BIOGEOGRAPHIC REGIONALIZATION MAP BASED IN CLIMATIC SUITABILITY

RESULTS – OAK SPECIES RICHNESS

Temperate Belt (Deciduous oak species)

Submediterranean Belt (Marcescent oak species)

RESULTS & DISCUSSION – *QUERCUS CANARIENSIS* SUITABLE AREAS (RS VS CLIMATIC)

FINAL REMARKS

- Demonstrated the close relationship between deciduous/marcescent potential areas with the temperate / mediterranean ecotone (submediterranean)
 - Oak species/functional groups are great models to infer on biogeographic delimitation
- Shed-light biogeographic boundaries with conservation insights on Iberian Forests
 - Perceptions on evolutionary biology and conservation planning
- Importance of integrative approaches in way to reduce biased analysis
 - RS variables boosts predictive model performance

Merci
Obrigado
Thank you
Muchas gracias